

What Conservatives Won't See & Liberals Won't Hear

A pure data analysis via ratios, looking at population perspectives, revealing a narrative no one wants to hear, see, say, or admit to.

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ABSTRACT: The story of the African-American (black) experience is complicated, painful, and difficult. You have extremes of truth on all sides, and therefore, extremes of lies. The media pushes a one-sided narrative, and the reactionary White, generally Christian and conservative base responds in a dismissive reaction. Meanwhile Black Lives Matter[®] ignores all cases not associated with deaths - justified or not - at the hands of white cops, up to and including condoning the deaths of black cops. Finally, the Police State reacts with a "Blue Lives Matter" self-defensive posture which downplays the true nature of the situation, and the actual horrors. Behind this is a story clearly too frightening for blacks to admit, too damning for cops to allow, too lucrative and useful for the media to fail to exploit, and too remote for "All Lives Matter" supporters to understand or see in the way that, rightly or wrongly, nine out of ten blacks have been taught and/or decided to see it: as a tribal and racial history. This paper therefore separates these three groups, and there is for homicides a control group of Hispanics, and compares them in stories created by ratios of ratios. These ratios elicit shocking but commonsensical details which can inform, sadden, and yet through enlightenment, maybe provide hope for America at a time of division.

Keywords - black, white, police, homicide, covid, overdose, hispanic

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Note from the Author (Preface and Disclaimer)

This article is not meant to hurt or offend anyone, but it probably will. If it does, like a good piece of art, it probably needs to. This article is written from a Libertarian/ Independent and Pro-America view, in which leftism is separated from liberalism, however, the title conveys a general direction rather than a specific group of people (save, perhaps, #BLM). The fact is that the entire discussion is a landmine, and yet someone has to wade through the landmine field to create some unity in the world. The data presented has never, to my knowledge, been shown this way because it involves a 3rd order analysis, whereas the best pro-right and pro-left soundbites come from 1st order analyses (covered in paper). “Lies, damned lies, and statistics.”

There are some hard facts covered in this paper that will be inconvenient **to both sides**. Should this paper wind up “fact checked” it will be important to note that they’d be fact-checking themselves, as the sources are FBI and Reuters fact-checks, as well as aggregating sites like Statista.

The author, also, rejects the Orwellian rewriting of history and language, such as redefining racism to benefit one group (definitely a racist thing to do), and historical bunk like the “1619 Project”¹, which has no sound scholarly basis. Politics does enter into this paper but through fact-based realities, such as the source of all Structural or Systemic Racism is the Democratic Party and Feudalism in general, which relies on plunder

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<https://www.forbes.com/sites/marybethgasman/2021/06/03/what-history-professors-really-think-about-the-1619-project/>

economies (piracy, slavery etc.) For without the Democratic Party there would be “no KKK, no racist USA.”² No Jim Crow, neither!³ That’s a hard pill to swallow. Almost as hard as explaining to a real liberal that Progressives are not liberal but Marxist.

The Marxism in “Social Justice” is well documented⁴, and need not be reiterated here except to point out the horrific reality that since Black Lives Matter⁵ and its Marxist, wife-beating leadership⁶ began the riots and CHAZ/CHOP⁷ (in Seattle), more children died at the hands of other black people, and more cops (half of them black) at the hands of BLM, than all the unarmed murders (justified or not) of black men in 2019.⁸ That’s a staggering fact as the riots only began approximately a month previous to this preface (June 2020)!

Real justice is **individual**, for the individual is the smallest minority. My sincere hope is that the rational, and level-headed, and what remains of an honest America can read this, and admit the data-driven truths, and overcome all biases, to seek some real solutions. Where inequality appears, such as

² BLM chants

³

<https://library.law.howard.edu/civilrightshistory/blackrights/jimcrow>

⁴ “The Uniqueness of Western Civilization,” R. Duchesne, 2011

⁵ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=boS5Tw4-F9U>

⁶

<https://abcnews.go.com/US/start-black-lives-matter-lgbt-g-lives/story?id=71320450>

⁷

<https://www.foxnews.com/us/portland-protest-autonomous-zone-tents-barricade-seattle-chop-chaz>

⁸

<http://legalinsurrection.com/2021/09/report-2020-antifa-blm-led-riots-injured-more-police-officers-caused-more-damage-and-resulted-in-more-arrests-than-the-capitol-riot/>

IQ⁹, there are reasons, and the data seems to show that it is not biological but a systemic denial of access and of family breakdown encouraged by welfarism.¹⁰

The sad aspect is that to understand one's world, one's problems, one needs IQ as an asset in order to react non-violently as violence is just a first, easy solution. Changing laws and school policies to permit violence, or lowered language standards, or excuse in-class racism from black children towards mixed race children¹¹ only admits to a form of "kid gloves" 'soft' racism, which treats black persons as inferior and child-like.¹² This, the author finds, is wholly unacceptable and frankly, disgusting¹³. It isn't the dream of great men like Martin Luther King, Thomas Sowell, Thurgood Marshall, or Frederick Douglas for their people to be treated as less than anyone.

Black History is American History, and anything else is a lie. But the idea of social Marxists that you can change history, or ignore facts, and just get rid (ie, burn) of it in order to "level the playing field" (actually tip it in others' favor based on race), is a lie as well. It's a dangerous lie, which only feeds white nationalism¹⁴ (not white pride¹⁵) and breeds more systemic racism in the Judicial System and media and other greater

⁹ <https://bit.ly/32nMOio>

¹⁰

<https://www.independentsentinel.com/black-professor-says-welfare-not-slavery-decimated-us-black-families/>

¹¹ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Sq8-K5McrhA>

¹² The "soft bigotry of low expectations."

<https://www.msn.com/en-us/news/us/professor-suspended-for-not-giving-black-students-easier-final-exam-sues-ucla/ar-AAP3dJu>

¹³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=m66rcHzWaPU>

¹⁴ Here differentiated from Patriotism while being white.

¹⁵ Gay pride is good. Black pride is good. But how is it that only white pride is racism and bad? This is the effect of the lies of social Marxists. White pride is as good or bad as any other. However, American Patriot or general Patriotic Pride is best of all. Love Thy Neighbor!

structures. Blacks who utilize/ appropriate white culture do far better than blacks in Africa (by average income), and there is no desire among African Americans to "return to Africa."¹⁶ In general, as a whole, the population simply wishes to be treated with respect. A few black supremacists¹⁷ wish to burn everything down and create violence and dissension and enslave other races and kill homosexuals¹⁸, but this is not the majority. It is only an extremely loud minority who have ties to communists and globalists.¹⁹

It is beyond the scope of this paper to go too deeply into the results of IQ data, or of black inventions²⁰ and history²¹, etc. The data shared here will just be in support of some point, the narratives will have to be sought in other papers.

Finally, I'd like to make a point that in my EPEMC works²² one thing that has become clear is how much white people have needed the almost unblemished knowledge and wisdom of black and brown peoples, to get the truth of cosmology. The best-recorded versions of history, outside of China or Mexico, come not from the esoteric roots of Whites (where many things were burned by the Catholic Church), but from the black peoples of Australia, the Dogon, or at sites in Egypt, or South Africa²³, and of the Tamil people in south India who are darker skinned

¹⁶

<https://www.thecrimson.com/article/1963/12/20/black-muslim-leader-urges-us-negroes/>

¹⁷ ie, Black Hebrew Israelites

¹⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=TsXBNwo2pNw>

¹⁹ Or peddle racist, unscientific ideas about melanin superiority

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8p0x0v9ndq8>

²⁰ <http://bit.ly/2HjVt9Z>

²¹ <https://bit.ly/3uHj5ph>

²² <https://sites.google.com/view/epemcgateway/epemc>

²³

https://www.academia.edu/42656690/Secret_Held_in_Maputo

than the Hindus of the north, and are considered lower in caste.

Furthermore it is worth noting that blacks and whites (and natives) in antebellum America owned slaves²⁴, mostly black, some white and native.²⁵ Indeed whites remained slaves in portions of the world into the 20th century.²⁶ But blacks are being enslaved **today** in North Africa²⁷, enabled by the leftist policies of the European Union and the racist institutions of Sharia.²⁸

Whiteness is not a thing. Privilege is a thing, but all races have privileges and disadvantages. In America, it is more of an advantage to be of Indian or Chinese descent than of European over African or Native descent (as measured by average income). All dualistic and Hegelian arguments lose their sheen upon close inspection. So for these comparisons we should solely rely upon **data** and not media driven narratives which have divided people. The rise of black supremacy, white supremacy, and all other bigotries come from propaganda created by dichotomies which ignore the potential for misunderstanding; or exploit it purposefully²⁹.

In this paper there are *two* forms of white on black crime and of black on white crime; two of cop on black murder and cop on

white murder, etc. Both sides have a story to share. But if you are not prepared for the facts of this story, you will be saddened, angered, or stupified. I take no responsibility for this, because it is up to the individual to be mature enough to deal with it.

SYNOPSIS

Young black men, and African Americans in general, have indeed a real complaint. Through 2nd order analysis, it is shown that Blacks are 22.8 times more likely than cops to be murdered by the other, as per the whole population rate (cops are 2.21 times more likely as per their own group rate, in vice versa). Also, blacks are 23.1 times more likely than white to be killed by cops, as per their racial populations. This is the beginning of the shocking data, shown in Figure 3.

But the story isn't monocular. While White on Black murder is 2.92 times more likely than vice versa in the racial grouping (RG), Black on White murder is 2.16 times more likely when compared with the whole population (WP), which makes the total numbers much higher. But Black on Black murder is **5.66** times more likely than White on White murder as per WP. This is truly terrifying. It's beyond the scope of the paper to consider the deep causes of inner city and intra-racial violence. For comparison Blacks are 4.43 times more likely to be murdered than Hispanics, in general. This shows it is truly an issue within the black community, not "People of Color."

Also, Whites are 5.81 times more likely to overdose as per WP (as per RG, they have nearly even rates of 15.2 and 14.0, per 100k, white and black respectively). Cops are also, white and black, killed at a rate of 6.01 per 100k in their group. Racially speaking,

²⁴

<https://www.theroot.com/did-black-people-own-slaves-1790895436>

²⁵ What no one seems to know though, is that according to the Sumerian myths both the Adamu and the Igigi were born into and *for* the purpose of slavery. They share in this history, and neither side is without sin. Many black people in America are more than 50% European by descent, or are of mixed race with other races, such as Asian, Indian, Mestizo, etc.

²⁶ <https://time.com/5042560/libya-slave-trade/>

²⁷

<https://nypost.com/2017/12/04/slave-auctions-in-libya-caught-on-camera/>

²⁸

<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/2158244019828849>

²⁹ "Grifting" and "race-baiting"

whites are actually more likely to be killed by cops at .12 vs .09 (WP) per 100k. White cops are also more likely to be killed than black cops 5.03 vs 1.13 per 100k in their groups! It must likely be surmised that this is in cross fire with blacks, mostly men, committing crimes, or in victimizing a few black males defending themselves, and it being still ruled a murder and not self-defense. But surely this latter is a very rare case, and the former is much higher.

As we shall see, though, the most frightening reality is revealed in Figure 5 which shows such a drastic difference between homicide experience for whites and blacks, and agree with a white population perspective, that changes the perspective completely. What it reveals is that a culture which encourages dropping out, and punishes those who seek to escape, makes it so that being a young black male is a game of Russian Roulette with crime, and of course, interaction with the Justice system, starting with cops. In such a situation, is it any surprise that being “about that life” has led to an increase, so precipitously, of a negative experience by only one race? According to the analysis in Figure 5, in 2013 the black homicide rate was 18.49 per 100k, (RG), while whites only experienced a racial rate of 2.40; that’s 6.26 times the rate of White on White homicide (WoW).

It gets even more frightening, for both. Within the white population grouping, (as per

a white perspective), Black on White (BoW) crime is 34.2% more likely than the reverse, while White on Black (WoB) crime is only 7.3% as likely as the reverse. This shows a likely bias will develop. But in the black population grouping, Black on White crime is 1368% likely over the reverse! Meanwhile it isn’t an innocent issue with whites, as (from the black perspective), WoB is 292% more likely than the reverse. So there is death on all fronts. WoW is only 89% as likely as BoB murder, as per their perspective... (it is 112% more likely from a white perspective), so how can it be avoided that seeing the situation is worse for them (and reminded of this by daily media distortions), and not hearing a similar feedback from white America, only leads to a suspicion that the System is against blacks pre-determinedly? Of course, it is not only, but as covered already, there is a clear difference in the deaths of blacks by cops and vice versa, as per RG and WG. Blacks are 7.69 times more likely to be murdered than whites (rate per 100k or RPK), and that is simply atrocious. This stat far outshines the remainder of that category (black vs white).

Both Figures 4 and 5 tell a story which reveals a terrible reality for black America that is not shared by white America. Now, what does it tell us about the common media and political narratives? This is what will be explored in the discussion body of the paper.

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DATA NARRATIVES REVEAL LIES BY MAINSTREAM SOURCES³⁰

Number vs. Cause

Figure 1 - Comparing Deaths (as of August 2020) - log scale

³⁰ <https://bit.ly/31V0SgL>

Rate/Population (100k)

Figure 2 - Rates by Population Comparison (log scale); Left to right, circles are 1 to 4

Figure 3 - 2nd Order Analysis (dividing groups by population, and by other groups)

Looking at the first two graphs, we can see where pick-n-choose narratives come from (rationalizations masquerading as justifications). For example there is a statistically 0 significance for the following:

- Unarmed black men killed by cops
- Unarmed white men killed by cops (however higher than the former)
- Black or white cops killed (as per race)
- Cops killed by gunfire (as a % of total homicides, not by group)
- And there is a nearly identical rate of overdose as per blacks and whites

However, there is an **incredible significance of difference**³¹ in the following arenas:

- Blacks vs. Whites killed by cops (as per their own race's population total)
- Blacks vs Cops killed (again as per their own group)

³¹ And a better statistician than I could show this with sigma work

- Black homicides total is far higher per race than total population, which is also higher than Whites or Hispanics
- Black on black homicides per race is far higher than it looks as per whole population, meaning that people are not cognizant of the extreme danger of growing up as a black [male] in a black neighborhood. (the Singleton Theory)
- Blacks killed by police as per race (the main narrative) is much higher a rate than versus whole population (the counter or conservative narrative) 23.1x
 - This appears to be because there are more committing crimes and homicides, or threatening police, etc.
- Black overdoses are worse as per population than white overdoses 15.2 v 14.0
- But white overdoses as per race are far worse a jump (5.8x as per whole population) than black overdoses, which explains why the media responds to the meth and fentanyl epidemic more than the crack epidemic.³²

Figure 4 - Homicide Rates, 3rd Order Analysis

Looking at this graph the most telling story is the difference in how whites experience homicide in their communities as compared to blacks. First, each race mostly murders within the race, that's well known and publicised by the conservative media. However, this ignores the sheer despair created by mostly "blue", mostly urban, mostly Democrat run areas (like Chicago, Baltimore, Philadelphia, Detroit, southside LA, etc.) where blacks are literally being slaughtered

³² Which makes Dave Chapelle's jokes about it, either ignorant, or cringe-worthy and strangely vindictive.

by one another (at very young average ages). However, not only is the rate higher, but is 6.3x higher than how white on white homicide appears. This means that it's easy to decry "gun violence" and garner support from people literally scared for their lives, and sell a form of one-sided politics (optically speaking).

From this graphical perspective, black on white homicide is far more hype-driven, when it is the black homicide rates (versus whole population and versus within the race) that matters the most in the discussion. It has nothing to do with cops, which is statistically non relevant.

Figure 5 - Racial Crime cross-comparison

Looking at this figure, Black on White death by homicide is far worse than white on black, which completely destroys the BLM narrative. There is 4.74x the significance of the Black on White vs White on Black than the reverse (the mainstream narrative), indicating a deep racial hatred, on average, within black communities for whites. In other words, if one had 5 black supremacists and 5 white supremacists, the chances are 4.74x higher that the black supremacist would commit homicide on the white supremacist, than in reverse. Which completely destroys the SPLC³³ and NAACP's narratives, for which "fact-checkers" are basing much of their race-baiting upon.

- ★ Black on White vs. White on Black is higher within the black population and total population
- ★ But as whites see it, White on White and Black on Black are the majority of instances

³³ Southern Poverty Law Center

Both of these narratives track with the Conservative media, proving that Breitbart, NY Post, etc. have been more forthright throughout the 2020-2021 riots and debacles. Honest, but deaf to innocent black lives.

Black lives [obviously] matter

But not only black lives.

Figure 6 - 3rd Order analysis involving police populations

- ❖ Blacks are far **more likely to die of overdose than via homicide** or by cops. Both white and black cops are far more likely to die than blacks are to die by police officers, unarmed or not. Blacks are slightly more likely to die via a black cop than a white cop (1.15x) disproving the BLM and liberal media agenda or narrative.
- ❖ Blacks are far, far more likely to be murdered by one another than by a white cop (7.67x more likely)
- ❖ Which means, if a black male, armed or unarmed, were to walk by 8 cops or 8 black males, they have a statistically more likely chance to be murdered by one of the black males than by a cop, white or black.
- ❖ White cops are also far more likely to be killed in the line of duty than the reverse: to kill a black male. Being killed as an unarmed black female by a police officer is so statistically unlikely that it's a wonder it happened to Breonna Taylor. It must have been almost pure self-defense from the police³⁴, or a freak accident, statistically speaking.

³⁴ <https://tatumreport.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/08/Breonna-Taylor-Summary-redacted.pdf>

Conclusions & Discussion

Looking across the graphs, especially the 2nd, we can see that the two narratives are both lies. However, the liberal narrative is far, far more disingenuous and emotionally manipulative than the reverse, which is mostly deaf, or blind, etc.

The bottom line is that the mathematical statistics are able to dispel, via 2nd and 3rd order ratio analysis, the lies of both sides, and get right at the truth.

There have been many new lies, about COVID, the election, Kyle Rittenhouse, etc. since these analyses were done. Yet the narratives have only become more entrenched, and the stats haven't really changed. What has changed is that more governments, local etc. have given up helping black students and young people to deal with the reality in general.

The more scary proposition is that the racism being fomented against whites by the media, through outright lies or ignorance, could make these stats worsen and worsen, until the alt-right (white supremacists) react. First they will recruit, and conflate patriotism with racial rhetoric, and then they will overwhelm. That is not the kind of result that a classical liberal such as myself who advocates for egalitarian and humanitarian values prefers. It would be nice if this math could make its way to the mainstream. But something tells this author, that as the New Cold War [asymmetric] agenda rolls forward, that it'd fall on deaf, or traitorous, ears.

Returning briefly to Figure 2, there is something to note. Group 1 (left) reveals a clear break-out in stats for black homicides in "vs. black" population. So, within the context of "the community" (who "shall overcome")

there is a clear struggle which the author empathizes with. But it is not caused by whites, but other blacks. This reveals why the #1 caller for police help is blacks, by far.³⁵ Which makes the BLM "defund the police"³⁶ narrative and agenda, particularly unpopular,³⁷ even with gangs in Long Beach, LA³⁸.

Group 3 reveals that black on white homicide and whites killed by cops are both fake narratives. The Left and the Right are lying on these issues. It's true that *some* of it happens, but not much. **Yet** unarmed whites killed by cops is far, far more common than unarmed blacks killed by cops (group 4). So Daniel Shavers was not an anomaly as the left media suggested when they deigned to respond to it at all.

Group 4 reveals the cops killed (according to their own population) is BS, as compared to the whites killed by cops, or blacks killed in homicides. In other words, either they have a strong lobby, or sympathy, or are using this narrative to create a justification for the rising Police State and the excuse for impunity for *occasional* but increasingly common abuse.

³⁵

<https://libertyunyielding.com/2020/06/06/blacks-call-police-for-help-7-times-as-frequently-as-whites-and-other-inconvenient-truths/>

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